

THE CONCEPT OF FACILITATION AND ITS SIGNIFICANCE IN PRIMARY CLASSES

Yolchiyeva Sh.O.

Doctoral student of Fergana State University

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Abstract. *Educating the young generation to become mature individuals in all respects is the biggest step taken for the development of the state. Creating new proposals according to the requirements of the time, which is developing by the second, is of great importance for the development of society.*

Keywords: *facilitation, facilitator, Pedagogue-facilitator, pedagogical neology, synegetic (new alternative) approach, acmeological (psychophysiological) approach, integrative work, individual work.*

INTRODUCTIONS

A number of changes are taking place in the education system of the Republic of Uzbekistan to further improve the level of quality, and as a necessary condition for this, the need to change the role of the teacher in the educational process to a modern one is highly felt. The need to organize teaching itself not as a transfer of information, but as a means of facilitating meaningful learning processes is highlighted. Therefore, the need for the introduction of the concepts of facilitation and facilitator in the educational process was felt and is widely used in the teaching process. Getting the young generation interested in learning from kindergarten and school, engaging them in the learning process through various games remains the first task for teachers. It is one of the most correct ways for qualified teachers to introduce children who have just left kindergarten to the classroom while their imaginations are in play.

LITERATURE ANALYSIS:

Each subject has its own research scientists of each field, and a number of scientists from around the world and Uzbekistan have studied and conducted research on the use of modern educational technologies and the facilitation approach in primary classes.

The concept of facilitation was brought into science and researched by psychologist Carl Rogers.

Our scientists have given different definitions and opinions to the term facilitation. Below are examples of them:

1. Facilitation - working through the development of independent thinking in students (F. Emer);
2. Facilitation - conducting work by forming mutually positive personal relationships among students (R. Shmak);
3. "Facilitation - working through synegetic (new alternative) and acmeological (psychophysiological) approaches (R.S. Dinmukhametov); "
4. "Facilitation - conducting psychological, integrative and individual work (I.V. Jijina);" Sh.R. Sanarova, F.O. Khodzhiyeva, O.P. among the scientists of our republic. Scientists such as Aslonova, T.R.Azlarov, H.YO.Najmiddinova, A.A.Abdukadirov studied various problems of using modern technologies in education. A number of research scientists, such as B.S. Gershunsky, Y.Y. Lysenko, Y.I. Mashbits, M.N. Perova, O.K. Tikhomirov, have dealt with the

issues of using modern technologies and approaches, various games in organizing the education of children of primary school age.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY:

The article provides insights into the process of teaching in primary classes based on the facilitation approach through modern educational technologies.

What is the concept of facilitation, what researches have been conducted by scientists who have studied it, and how high results can be achieved when taught through this approach.

ANALYZES AND RESULTS:

What is facilitation, what meaning is hidden behind it? Facilitation is a special management style that includes the creation of such a management system and the organization of a pedagogical process, in which management has a directive nature and does not go beyond the scope of self-organization of the self-management system. Simply put, facilitation is both a process and a way of doing things, as well as a means of organizing high-quality and effective group interactions, group cooperation and joint activities.

"The word facilitation is a word taken from the English language "facilitate" which means "facilitating", "stimulating", "creating favorable conditions".

If we analyze the concept of facilitator based on the sources, this concept was introduced into science by classical psychologist Carl Rogers. The English word "facilitate" means "to ease, to cooperate". So, the main task of the teacher is to facilitate and at the same time stimulate the educational activity, i.e. to create the necessary intellectual and emotional environment and psychological support in the group.

Facilitation in the school education system is aimed at creating a comfortable environment in the room that ensures a positive impact on students, increasing students' confidence in their own strength, encouraging the need for independent work and should be understood as a method of developmental education in the way of support. Facilitation activities can be used in the school system in both primary and upper grades. But the importance of this process used in primary classes is several times higher than in upper classes. Because through this process, the children's interest in the lesson increases several times, which helps them to achieve a high level of education. The person who creates the facilitation process and manages it is called a facilitator.

In the field of education, this place belongs to the teacher. His task is not to show himself as a governor, but to take a neutral position and guide students to study knowledge with sufficient accuracy and in the right direction of development. The activity of a pedagogue-facilitator has a beneficial effect on the development of initiative and independence of students, forms communicative interaction skills, and helps to create a comfortable environment for communication between students during the educational process. is a person who helps to create an environment. In this case, the educational process is characterized by the use of methods and technologies that save freedom and health.

A teacher-facilitator is a person-centered approach to education and an empathetic caregiver of students' feelings, inner experiences, abilities and potential, activities and actions, encouraging their success and service. , a teacher with a confident attitude. Facilitator is a special tool in the educational process. The effectiveness of the development of the educational institution and the educational system as a whole depends on the qualification and professional skills of the facilitator. He will be taught psychological interaction skills and effective communication technologies.

Figure 1. Facilitator characteristics

In the process of facilitation, research is carried out in order to make the team work harmoniously and efficiently, to create new things or to acquire theoretical scientific information, and then to find its practical application. Team work and team interaction are organized through special actions of the teacher. Facilitation refers to the process of making these actions easier. The leader takes the priority position in it.

CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS:

Improving the social activity of students on the basis of pedagogical neology in the primary education system, using an easy and convenient way to achieve the intended goal in every way, increasing their social activity related to subjects, students in the educational process from a scientific and theoretical point of view the fundamental reform of participation is of great pedagogical significance. It is worth noting that the world experience of information and communication technologies and the widespread penetration of the Internet into the field of education opens a great way for the globalization of educational services.

Every subject taught in primary school is very important for children. In order to teach these subjects in depth, it is necessary to choose an explanatory method that is understandable to children and to apply it in practice. Today, the increase of modern technologies requires further improvement of modern education. The reason is that today's children understand technologies very well and have already developed management skills. For such children, the old methods are not interesting and are not effective enough to attract their attention during the lesson. Therefore, modern teachers should also be familiar with modern technologies and be able to use new modern teaching methods through them. In order to carry out these activities, teachers are required to study and research incessantly. In order to further improve this process, the use of a facilitation approach serves to achieve sufficient results.

REFERENCES

1. R.A. Mavlonova, N.H. Rakhmonkulova, K.O. Matnazarova, M.K. Shirinov, S. Hafizov. "General pedagogy" Science and technology "publisher 2018

2. N.M. Kuchkarova, S.S. Otayeva, A.R. Amangeldiyeva, SH.O. Yolchiyeva, "Pedagogical skills" Booknomy Print publishing house, 2024
3. N. Orinova "Innovative educational technologies and foreign experience in primary grades" educational methodological complex., Fergana 2020.
4. Jumayev M.E." Methodical-mathematical training of future elementary school teachers in the development of the student as a creative person". - Tashkent: Science and technology, 2009
5. Tadzhiyeva Z.G. Use of historical materials in primary grade mathematics lessons". - Tashkent: Uzkomsentr, 2003.
6. Dimukhametov R.S. Facilitation — a new role methodist (prepodavatelia) instituta povyshenia qualificatsii // Vestn. Chelyab. Mr. ped. flour Sir. 3, Actual problems of education of the rising generation. — 2004. — No. 26. — S. 226-236. (0.7 p.l.)
7. Jihina I.V. Psikhologicheskie osobennosti razvitiya fasilitatsii pedagoga: diss. ... candy. psycho. date: 19.00.07 / I.V. Gijina. - Yekaterinburg: Uralsky Gos. prof.-ped. un-t, 2000. — 153 p.
8. Ya. Nurumbekova, D. Toshtemirov, Yo. Fakhriddinov. General pedagogy. Textbook. — GulDU-2022
9. [http://kompy.info/a-i-gersen-nomidiga-rossiya-davlat-pedagogika-universiteti tos.html?page=29](http://kompy.info/a-i-gersen-nomidiga-rossiya-davlat-pedagogika-universiteti/tos.html?page=29)
10. [http://www.hozir.org/topic 19 teacher's preparation for the lesson html page=3](http://www.hozir.org/topic_19_teacher's_preparation_for_the_lesson.html)
11. General Andijan State University named after <https://hozir.org/z-m-babur> pedagogy html page=13